

Face Detection on profile picture using MTCNN Algorithm

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Abstract: This paper presents a face detection using multi-task cascading convolutional network (MTCNN) method, especially for face images. By recognizing the presence of a face, the goal is to ensure the integrity of the user's profile picture. The system leverages the efficiency and accuracy of MTCNN to upload profile images and verify the presence of a face. If no face is found or more than one face is found, the user will be asked to upload a new photo. The system uses preprocessing to prepare the image for input into the MTCNN model for face detection. By integrating these solutions into the website, users can optimize the accuracy of their profile pictures, thus improving their experience.

Keywords: MTCNN algorithm, image prioritization, face detection, profile picture and user authentication.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this digital age, social media and business websites have become important resources for people to connect and share information. However, it can be difficult to verify the accuracy of information provided on these platforms, including profile images. Facial recognition technology can solve this problem by using machine learning algorithms to identify faces in images. By integrating facial detection algorithms into websites, users can have greater confidence in the accuracy of the profile information they encounter. This enhancement is designed to improve the overall user experience and provide users with reliable information. As a result, the integration of facial detection into professional websites is important to increase the accuracy and reliability of profile information.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

M et al.[1] provides an in-depth analysis of the state-of-the-art techniques for face detection using deep learning. The authors have discussed utilizing the Java programming language and OpenCV's Haar cascade classifier to detect faces in digital photos and improve investigation accuracy through grayscale image transformation.

Bilahari [2] provides a comprehensive review of face detection method on profile picture. The author used the Viola-Jones algorithm and Haar Cascade algorithm is selected as face detection algorithm. The model is trained on a dataset of images and when the user uploads a

profile picture the model detects multiple faces or the presence of human face.

Sirivarshitha et al.[3] proposed an approach for face detection and face recognition using OpenCV and face recognition libraries in Python. The author proposes a method for facial recognition systems and mathematical face print conversion stored in a database for identification. They emphasize the significance of automated face detection and recognition systems in various applications.

Jais [4] provides an in-depth analysis of the face detection technique. The author has used the Haar cascade classification technique which has predefined dataset stores in XML format. This classifier works by converting real-time face RGB colors using OpenCV into grayscale and comparing the resulting image with the dataset.

Raj [5] proposed age and gender estimation from facial recognition using OpenCV. The author uses a convolutional neural network (CNN) model and residual network architecture for the recognition for better accuracy. The author also says about the process involved in using weights by the pre-trained model.

III. MTCNN ALGORITHM

The Multi-Task Cascaded Convolutional Networks (MTCNN) algorithm represents a breakthrough in face detection, revolutionizing the way facial features are identified and localized in images. Unlike traditional methods, MTCNN utilizes a hierarchical architecture consisting of multiple stages, each dedicated to different tasks such as face candidate detection, facial landmark localization, and bounding box regression. This multi-stage approach allows MTCNN to effectively handle various challenges encountered in face detection, including variations in pose, illumination, and occlusion, leading to more accurate and reliable results.

One of the key advantages of MTCNN is its versatility and adaptability across different domains and applications. From security surveillance systems to social media platforms and augmented reality applications, MTCNN's robust performance

makes it a go-to solution for a wide range of use cases requiring facial analysis. Its integration with deep learning frameworks and computer vision libraries further simplifies its implementation, enabling developers to leverage its capabilities withease.

IV.METHODOLOGY

1. Data Collection:

The process initiates with the collection of image data, primarily through user uploads of profile pictures. These images are acquired through the Django framework, where users submit their profile pictures via the web interface.

2. Data Pre-Processing:

Upon receiving the uploaded images, the data undergoes pre-processing steps within the Python environment. Using OpenCV and NumPy libraries, the images are decoded and converted to a suitable format for analysis. If the image is in a non-standard format, it is converted to RGB format for consistency.

3. Face Detection:

Face detection is performed using the MTCNN (Multi-Task Cascaded Convolutional Neural Network) algorithm. This deep learning-based model excels in detecting faces within images. Leveraging the MTCNN library, the algorithm identifies facial features, such as eyes, nose, and mouth, with high accuracy.

4. Feature Detection:

The MTCNN algorithm applies a set of neural networks to the pre-processed images, effectively identifying and localizing facial features. This process generates bounding boxes around the detected faces, providing precise coordinates for further analysis.

5. Face Counting:

Following feature detection, the number of detected faces is evaluated to ensure compliance with application requirements. If the algorithm identifies more than one face or fails to detect any faces, an error message is displayed to the user, prompting them to provide a suitable profile picture.

6. Final Output:

Upon successful detection of a single face in the profile picture, the image is considered valid and suitable for further use. The image can then be utilized within the application as the user's profile picture, providing a seamless user experience. Additionally, the image may be stored for future reference or analysis, contributing to the functionality of the application.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

Import the package that are necessary.

```
import cv2
```

```
import numpy as np
```

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```
from mtcnn import MTCNN  
cv2 is used for reading and processing the input image,  
while np is used for converting the input data to a NumPy  
array format.
```

```
if isinstance(photo_id, np.ndarray):
```

```
    img = cv2.imdecode(photo_id,  
cv2.IMREAD_UNCHANGED)
```

```
elif hasattr(photo_id, 'read'):
```

```
    img = cv2.imdecode(np.frombuffer(photo_id.read(),  
np.uint8), cv2.IMREAD_UNCHANGED)
```

```
else: raise ValueError("Invalid image  
format.")
```

```
detector = MTCNN()
```

```
faces = detector.detect_faces(img)
```

```
if len(faces) == 0:
```

```
    raise ValueError("No face detected in the  
uploaded image.")
```

```
if len(faces) > 1:
```

```
    raise  
    ValueError("Multiple faces detected.  
Please upload a photo with only one face.")
```

```
if is_blurry(img):
```

```
    raise ValueError("Image is blurry. Please  
upload a clear photo.")
```

VI.RESULT

The function first checks if any faces were detected. If no faces were detected, it returns a message indicating that no faces were found and suggests that the user upload a photo with a human face . If image is blurry then it suggest to upload a clear photo.If more than one face is detected, it returns a message indicating that multiple faces were found and suggests that the user upload a photo with only one person in it.

Based on various benchmarks and studies, the MTCNN (Multi-Task Cascaded Convolutional Neural Network) algorithm has demonstrated robust performance in detecting human faces in images. It is known for its

effectiveness in detecting faces across a wide range of conditions, including variations in lighting, pose, and occlusion. MTCNN generally achieves high accuracy levels, particularly in scenarios with clear facial features

Fig:1

Fig:2

Fig.3

Fig.4

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have demonstrated the importance of implementing face detection on a website to verify the authenticity of profile pictures uploaded by users. We have assured that each profile photo has precisely one face by preprocessing submitted profile pictures before using the algorithm and developing a face identification model using the

MTCNN. In order to improve the precision and dependability of profile data, it may be possible to develop this project in the future by adding other features like emotion recognition or age estimation. Overall, this study provides proof of the strength of machine learning algorithms and their potential to significantly enhance our daily lives.

VIII. REFERENCES

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